

Species	Tissue	Accession number	Identity	Reference	
<i>Carassius auratus</i>	Olfactory epithelium	AM928511	77% <i>ogn1</i>	Krasnov et al., 2012 doi: 10.1186/1471-2164-13-130 Kessels et al., 2014, PubMed: 24608635 He et al., 2014, doi: 10.1530/JOE-13-0488 Ibarz et al., 2013, doi:10.1007/s10126-013- 9513-4	
<i>Danio rerio</i>	Myoblast	CT620959	75% <i>ogn1</i>		
<i>Gasterosteus aculeatus</i>	Eyes	DN691791	67% <i>ogn1</i>		
<i>Salmo salar</i>	Fast muscle	DY467584	81% <i>ogn1</i>		
<i>Salmo salar</i>	Thyroid	EG868446	63% <i>ogn1</i>		
<i>Salmo salar</i>	Skin	-	-		
<i>Danio rerio</i>	Fin	EV761307	77% <i>ogn1</i>		
<i>Danio rerio</i>	Postcranial axial skeleton	-	-		
<i>Danio rerio</i>	Pituitary	-	-		
<i>Sparus aurata</i>	Skin/scales	-	-		
<i>Gadus morhua</i>	Digestive tissue	FF416230	71% <i>ogn1</i>		
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Skin	GR683533	82% <i>ogn1</i>		
<i>Haplochromis sp.</i>	Jaw	BJ695864	75% <i>ogn2</i>		
<i>Salmo salar</i>	Thymus	EG772938	72% <i>ogn2</i>		
<i>Salmo salar</i>	Thyroid	EG869322	70% <i>ogn2</i>		
<i>Salmo salar</i>	Head kidney	EG900788	70% <i>ogn2</i>		
<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>	Spleen	FM024708	67% <i>ogn2</i>		
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Skeletal muscle	GR688606	83% <i>ogn2</i>		